

Unsupervised Learning for refactoring pattern detection

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I. QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

In order to improve the qualitative aspect of our experiments, we are providing, for each pattern, a possible situation that explains why this pattern may occur.

Pattern 1: Compositions of EM with low and moderate frequencies (Cluster 0): The developer wants to modularize the class by extracting some methods using EM. The main direction of EM is to create new methods to modularize functionalities, but in some situations some pieces of code may fit in an existing functionality already defined in a method of the class. This lead to an IM application, what could explain why this is the most frequently refactoring found with EM. Moreover, the developer might find the same functionality (just modularized in the new method) in methods in other classes. This could explain the refactorings where methods were moved to the class (PDT, PUT and MMT). Similarly, the developer might find a functionality that is related to other class. This could explain the refactorings where methods were moved from the class (PDS, PUS and MMS).

Pattern 2: Compositions of PUS with high frequency (Cluster 1): The developer wants to reorganize a hierarchy. The main direction is moving away many methods from the subclass to an existing superclass. They might be treated in the subclass but actually make more sense in the superclass. In some cases, it will be moved for a new superclass, which explain the occurrence with ES. The functionalities of the class might also be reorganized with the application of EM and IM. Moreover, some incoherent methods might be also moved from it using MMS. It explains the occurrence of PUS with EM, IM and MMS.

Pattern 3: Compositions of ES with low frequency and compositions of PUS with low and moderate frequencies (Cluster 2): The developer wants to reorganize a hierarchy as well as in Pattern 2. The main difference is that the reorganization mainly includes the creation of a new class, which is the reason why the ES refactoring is found with PUS. In this case, PUS is found with low and moderate frequencies which can be explained by the fact that a class is extracted (by applying ES) by pulling up common methods (methods with the same signature) in the subclasses. These methods are usually lower in number than not common methods. Other reasons could be a low number of methods in need of refactoring or even a low number of methods in the subclass.

Pattern 4: Compositions of refactorings of all types with

low frequency (Cluster 3): The developer wants to reorganize the whole class. In this situation, there is no specific reason such as modularize a functionality or reorganize a hierarchy, but to reorganize the whole class. This could explain the application of different refactorings.

Pattern 5: Compositions of MMT with moderate and high frequencies (Cluster 4): The developer selects a class to focus in an specific functionality. In this sense, many methods are moved to this target class. An example of this is a controller class, which is class concentrating many methods related to one functionality.

Pattern 6: Compositions of EM with high and moderate frequencies (Cluster 5): The developer wants to modularize the class by extracting many methods using EM. This situation is very similar to Pattern 1, but considers the extraction of a significant number of methods. This could be explained by the need of a better modularization or even by a class with more methods.

Pattern 7: Compositions of PUS with moderate and high frequencies (Cluster 6): The developer wants to reorganize a hierarchy as well in Pattern 2. The main difference is the inclusion of the moderate frequency. It could be explained by a lower need of reorganization or even the existence of smaller classes.